

Microservices-migrations

52 responses

How long do you work closely to software development?

52 out of 52 answered

And how long do you work closely with microservices migrations?

52 out of 52 answered

Which of the following describes your role / title best?

51 out of 52 answered

What region do you primarily work in currently?

52 out of 52 answered

What type of software are you primarily working on?

52 out of 52 answered

In which industry are you operating at?

52 out of 52 answered

Do you have any experiences of migrating a system towards microservices?

52 out of 52 answered

Did your organization's agile practices improve / got refined during or after the migration towards microservices?

50 out of 52 answered

 3.5 Average rating

Did your organization's testing process improve / got refined during or after the migration towards microservices?

51 out of 52 answered

 3.6 Average rating

Are there less dependencies between teams during or after the migration towards microservices (and therefore less waiting time)?

52 out of 52 answered

 3.5 Average rating

Did the alignment of software development with business analysis (of requirements) change significantly during or after the migration?

52 out of 52 answered

2.9 Average rating

How did you learn about what you and your organization can benefit from microservices?

52 out of 52 answered

What is microservices enabling your organization's business side to do (that before was not possible)?

51 out of 52 answered

How did you validate the value that microservices bring to your organization's business?

52 out of 52 answered

What did microservices enable your organization do **in a better way than before?**

52 out of 52 answered

11

Other

0.0% / 0 resp.

Order the benefits below with the most important on top and the least important at the end (based on your opinion).

51 out of 52 answered

Cost optimization of technical resources through the deployment of a subset of functionality in each client

Flexibility in skill-set and programming skills of engineers

Less duplicated functionality

Scalability

Centralized and continuous deployment instead of on premise installation with configuration overhead

Robustness / Rigidity of the system

Faster on-boarding of new recruits

Maintainability

Having a more lightweight application

Cost optimization of development

What is your high-level migration strategy?

51 out of 52 answered

What did you reuse from the old system and how?

51 out of 52 answered

Based on what ways did you split your microservices?

51 out of 52 answered

Order the ways of defining your microservices, starting with the most important on top and the least important at the end (based on your opinion).

46 out of 52 answered

Based on functionality

54.35 %
25

1

39.13 %
18

2

6.52 %
3

3

Based on features

39.13 %
18

1

43.48 %
20

2

17.39 %
8

3

Based on the structure of our teams

6.52 %
3

1

17.39 %
8

2

76.09 %
35

3

Which of the following activities did you perform in the migration?

52 out of 52 answered

Sort these activities in a reasonable chronological order, the first one on top and the last one on the bottom.

47 out of 52 answered

Split or refactor Database

Split or refactor Back-end

Split or refactor Front-end

Split Teams

Setup DevOps infrastructure

Setup microservices communications

Are teams becoming flexible in where to dedicate their time? (e.g. on features requested from customers urgently?)

52 out of 52 answered

 3.7 Average rating

Are teams after the migration structured based on parts of the system? (e.g. front-end team, back-end team, database team)

52 out of 52 answered

 3.5 Average rating

Are teams after the migration structured based on the functionality of the system (based on features)?

52 out of 52 answered

 3.3 Average rating

How is the migration managed in the organization?

52 out of 52 answered

How does personnel develop their skills in order to adapt on the migration?

50 out of 52 answered

Would you chose microservices again, if you could go back in time?

52 out of 52 answered

